

The Impact of Cathode Material Engineering on Electrical Characteristics of a Novel nanoscale Vacuum Field Emission Transistors

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Abstract: In this article, the effect of cathode material engineering as an important structural and physical parameter in the optimal design of nanoscale vacuum field emission transistors is presented and investigated. The calculation results show that by using different materials and reducing the cathode work function from 5.65 eV (platinum) to 4.28 eV (aluminum), the anode current has increased significantly by about 144%, while the threshold voltage of the device has been reduced by more than half. The operating frequency of the device with the reduction of the cathode work function is obtained at about 1.63 THz, which indicates the remarkable performance of the device in high-frequency applications. Other electrical characteristics such as I_{on}/I_{off} , V_{TH} , and g_m have also been calculated, and their changes with cathode material engineering have been investigated. This study can pave the way for a new generation of fast and low-power transistors for digital applications.

Keywords: Nanoscale Vacuum Field Emission Transistor, Finger Gate, Electrical characteristics, Cathode Material Engineering.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, vacuum micro- and nanoelectronic devices have attracted a lot of attention due to their significant advantages compared to solid-state electronics [1][2]. By using vacuum electronics, it is possible to manufacture new devices that were not possible in semiconductor electronics, and advantages such as high speed and low energy dissipation due to ballistic transport of electrons in

vacuum structures have been achieved. The use of vacuum channel devices, due to ballistic transport of carriers in the vacuum channel, has advantages such as speed and long life [3]. By eliminating dispersion in the channel, it is possible to achieve good performance in the high frequency range. Accordingly, there has been a great enthusiasm for the use of vacuum devices in the last 50 years. This interest has created a new branch in vacuum technology, called vacuum micro- and nanoelectronic devices. These devices are typically fabricated using advanced semiconductor manufacturing processes and can be operated at room temperature. Accordingly, nanometer-scale vacuum-channel field-emission transistors (VFETs) with cutoff frequencies around terahertz have been fabricated [4]. In addition, in high-temperature and high-radiation environments, vacuum electronic devices have higher electrical performance with higher reliability compared to solid-state devices [5]. In order to improve the performance of VFETs, different structures such as planar [6], vertical-channel [7], and finger-gate (FGVFET) [8] have been introduced and fabricated. Each of them has its own dimensions, manufacturing process, different geometry, and materials used. Therefore, there is a lack of a comprehensive study on the effect of geometric and physical characteristics on the performance of VFETs. Therefore, in this paper, a comprehensive study is conducted to investigate the effect of an important structural and physical parameter in FGVFETs. For this purpose, the FGVFET structure is examined by changing the cathode material and the electrical performance is presented by calculating the anode current (I_{anode}), gate current (I_{gate}), threshold voltage (V_{TH}), transfer conductance (g_m), geometric gate-anode capacitance (C_{ga}), and cutoff frequency (f_T) with the aim of improving the electrical characteristics.

2. Device structure and modeling method

Figure (1) shows the schematic of the proposed FGVFET device. In this device, a new metal-insulator-metal structure is proposed, which has significant advantages in electrical characteristics compared to conventional metal-insulator-semiconductor structures [9], [10]. In a previous study by the authors of this paper [11], the cathode-gate oxide thickness is 2 nm and the gate-anode oxide thickness is 26 nm. The vacuum channel length is 100 nm and its depth is 50 nm. The gate material is initially made of aluminum. The thickness of the anode and cathode is 5 nm. The distance between the anode and cathode is considered to be less than the mean free path of electrons in vacuum. In this device, the electron emission process in a strong electric field is expressed by the Fowler-Nordheim tunneling mechanism. The current density in this mechanism is expressed as equations (1) to (3) [12]:

(1)	$J = a_{FN} F^2 \exp\left(\frac{-b_{FN}}{F}\right)$
(2)	$a_{FN} = \frac{A}{1.1\varphi} \exp\left(\frac{10.4}{\sqrt{\varphi}}\right)$
(3)	$b_{FN} = 0.95B\varphi^{\frac{3}{2}}$

In these equations, J (A/cm^2) is the emitted current density, F (V/cm) is the electric field at the cathode, φ (eV) is the cathode work function and $A=1.56 \times 10^{-6}$ and $B= 6.87 \times 10^7$.

Figure 1: Schematic of the finger gate device. A) 3D view. B) Finger gate structure from top view [8]

To study this vertical vacuum channel transistor, the 3D electrostatic and particle analysis program CST Studio based on the finite integration (FIT) method has been used. To extract the electrical characteristics of the device, first the electric field distribution for the applied bias has been calculated. Then, using the extracted data for the electric field in all meshes, the current has been calculated using the Fowler-Nordheim tunneling mechanism and following the path of the electrons emitted from the cathode. The electrons emitted from the cathode either collide with the anode/oxide/gate regions in the device or with the upper or lower boundaries in the $x/y/z$ axes. When all the collisions have been made, the path of the emitted electrons is followed and the current of each region is obtained using the collision events.

3. Results and Discussion

Cathode material engineering can be considered as one of the main solutions for controlling the threshold voltage in FGVFET devices, because based on the Fowler-Nordheim tunneling mechanism, the device current density in equation (1) depends on the cathode material work function. For this purpose, in order to investigate the effect of changing the cathode material on the electrical characteristics of the device, we have considered the cathode electrode made of metals with different work functions, including aluminum, titanium, copper, gold, and platinum. Figure 2-a shows the device transfer characteristic curve (anode current versus gate voltage) with changing the cathode material for a fixed anode voltage ($V = 5$), and Figure 2-b shows the anode current and gate leakage current as a function of the work function of the cathode material. As can be seen in Figure 2, by reducing the cathode work function from 5.65 eV (platinum) to 4.28 eV (aluminum), the anode current increases significantly by about 144%. This can be attributed to the change in the height of the tunneling barrier at the cathode-vacuum interface. The lower the cathode work function, the lower the height and thickness of the tunneling barrier, and as a result, the probability of electron tunneling increases, which in turn increases the on-state current of the device [13]. Given the importance of gate leakage current in device performance, the effect of changes in the cathode work function on the gate leakage current in Figure 2-b is a study of the FGVFET structure. In vertical channel devices, the collision of electrons emitted from the cathode on the left side with the gate on the right side and vice versa is known to be the main factor in generating gate leakage current, and accordingly, the finger gate structure was introduced as an effective solution to reduce leakage current [8]. Simulation results on this structure show that by reducing the cathode work function from 5.65 eV (platinum) to 4.28 eV (aluminum), the gate leakage current increases from 0.18 nA to 19 nA. This phenomenon is

due to the decrease in the height of the field emission barrier at the cathode-vacuum channel interface. This increases the number of electrons emitted from the cathode on the left side that collide with the gate on the right side (and vice versa), and as a result, the gate leakage current increases.

Figure 2: a) Anode current characteristic curve in terms of gate voltage for changes in cathode work function $V = 5V$ b) Anode current and gate current for changes in cathode material work function

Table (1) shows the results of changes in the electrical characteristics of V_{TH} , g_m , f_T and the on-to-off current ratio (I_{on}/I_{off}) by changing the cathode material in the FGVFET device. By reducing the cathode work function, the threshold voltage of the device is reduced by more than half because the height of the field emission barrier at the cathode-vacuum location is reduced. The lower the height and thickness of the field emission barrier for electron tunneling from the cathode to the vacuum, the greater the probability of electron tunneling and, as a result, the threshold voltage decreases [13]. The transfer conductance in this device is calculated from equation (4) for a constant anode voltage [8]. By reducing the work function, the value of g_m increases significantly due to the increase in the on-state current of the device, so that by using aluminum as the cathode electrode, g_m reaches 76 μS , which is 380 times larger than the g_m reported in reference [4].

$$(4) \quad g_m = \frac{dI_a}{dV_g} a_{FN}$$

$$(5) \quad f_T = \frac{g_m}{2\pi C_{ga}}$$

Table 1: Electrical Characteristics of FGVFET by Changing Cathode Material

Cathode Workfunction (eV)	g_m (μ S)	C_{ga} (aF)	f_t (THz)	V_{th} (V)	$I_{on}/I_{off} \times 10^5$
Al (4.28)	76	7.42	1.63	0.423	1.83
Ti (4.33)	73	7.42	1.56	0.431	2.15
Cu (4.65)	63	7.42	1.35	0.575	5.99
Au (5.1)	49	7.42	1.05	0.806	26
Pt (5.65)	35	7.42	0.75	1.088	16.1

In the FGVFET device, due to the ballistic transport of carriers in the vacuum channel, according to equation (5), the value of f_T depends only on g_m and C_{ga} [11], as can be seen, with a decrease in the work function, the value of f_T increases and reaches 1.63 THz for an aluminum work function of 4.28 eV, which is 3.5 times larger than that of the reference planar device [4]. The reason for this can be attributed to the increase in g_m . The study of C_{ga} for changes in the cathode work function shows that this capacitance remains constant at a value of 42.7 aF, because the gate-anode capacitance depends on the structure geometry. In addition, in Table (1), the changes in the on-to-off current ratio (I_{on}/I_{off}) of the aforementioned device are reported with respect to the cathode work function. The results show that the decrease in the work function has caused a decrease in the I_{on}/I_{off} ratio. Although the I_{on} content has increased, as the barrier height decreases, the probability of electron tunneling from the cathode in the off state of the device also increases (increasing I_{off}). Therefore, the I_{on}/I_{off} ratio has generally decreased but is still within the range of conventional MOSFET structures.

6. References

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